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Filtering Methods for Efficient Dynamic Access Control Under Massive Machine-Type Communication Scenarios in 5G Networks

Israel Leyva-Mayorga *

Instituto ITACA, Universitat Politècnica de València, Camino de Vera, s/n, 46022, Valencia, Spain; {isleyma, marodrig,vpla,jmartinez}@upv.es

* Correspondence: isleyma@upv.es; Tel.: +34 96 387 70 00, Ext. 73005

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1 Featured Application: Dynamic access control in cellular networks.

Abstract: One of the three main use cases of 5G networks is massive machine-type communications. The latter refers to the highly synchronized accesses to the cellular base stations from a great number of wireless devices, as a product of the automated exchange of small amounts of data. Clearly, an efficient mMTC is a required to support the Internet of Things (IoT). Nevertheless, the method to change from idle to connected mode, known as the random access procedure, of 4G has been directly inherited by 5G, at least, until the first phase of standardization. Research has demonstrated the random access procedure is inefficient to support mMTC, hence, access control schemes are needed to obtain an adequate performance. In this paper, we compare the benefits of using different filtering methods to configure an access control scheme included in the 5G standards: the access class barring (ACB), according to the intensity of access requests. These filtering methods are a key component of our proposed ACB configuration scheme, which can lead to more than a three-fold increase in the probability of successfully completing the random access procedure under the most typical network configuration and mMTC scenario.

Keywords: Access class barring (ACB); adaptive algorithms; Internet of Things (IoT); massive machine-type communication (mMTC); recursive-least squares (RLS)

17 1. Introduction

The first phase of standardization for the future 5th generation of mobile networks (5G) was concluded in the Release 15 of the 3GPP Evolved Universal Terrestrial Radio Access (E-UTRA) specifications [1]. Previous mobile generations, 3G and 4G, have merely focused on providing a faster and better mobile broadband. Instead, 5G relies on three main use cases: massive machine-type communication (mMTC), enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB), and ultra-reliable low-latency communication (URLLC). The support for mMTC and URLLC are the main distinctive characteristics of 5G, and are expected to enable a great number of novel applications. These include, among others, the Internet of Things (IoT), where every daily-life object is connected to the Internet to empower a great deal of functionalities.

Nevertheless, the Release 15 of the 3GPP specifications introduced few advances in terms of mMTC support when compared to Release 14. One of the most critical requirements to efficiently support mMTC in 5G was to introduce enhancements to the random access procedure (RAP) of 4G. The RAP is the method used by the wireless devices, known as user equipments (UEs), to switch

31 from idle to connected mode. In other words, it is the method used by the UEs for initial access to the
32 cellular network.

33 Several studies have demonstrated the inefficacy of the RAP, as defined by the 3GPP [1], to support
34 mMTC in 4G [2–5]. Specifically, severe congestion can occur when a bulk of UE access attempts occur
35 in a highly synchronized manner. The latter is a typical behavior in mMTC applications that is likely
36 to exceed the signaling capacity of the cellular base station (BS). Since the RAP remains the same in 5G,
37 the same limitations and problems persist.

38 Enhancements are expected to be introduced to the RAP in the following standardization phases
39 of 5G. However, due to the need for backward compatibility with 4G, it remains uncertain whether
40 these will be sufficient to support mMTC applications efficiently. On the other hand, access control
41 schemes present an appealing solution to congestion. Because of this, a wide range of access control
42 schemes have been proposed in the literature [6–11].

43 One of the most promising access control schemes is the access class barring (ACB); hence, it
44 has been included in the LTE-A Radio Resource Control (RRC) specifications [1]. The ACB scheme
45 redistributes the UE access attempts through time. For this, each UE may delay the beginning of
46 its RAP according to the barring parameters: barring rate and mean barring time. If the barring
47 parameters are correctly configured, sporadic periods of congestion can be relieved in exchange for a
48 longer access delay. This is true, even if barring parameters are selected beforehand, and remain fixed
49 throughout the congestion period [5,10,12,13]. However, congestion is a transitory phenomenon, so
50 an adequate performance under several conditions can only be obtained by continuously adapting
51 the barring parameters to the intensity of access attempts. Doing otherwise would increase the access
52 delay of UEs during intervals in which no congestion occurs, but also fail to relieve congestion episodes
53 that are more severe than expected. Needless to say, correctly configuring the barring parameters in
54 real-time is a complicated task.

55 Numerous methods to continuously adapt the barring parameters have been proposed in the
56 literature [9,14–18]; we refer to these methods simply as ACB configuration (ACBC) schemes. In theory,
57 some of these schemes can lead to a near-optimal performance in terms of success probability (i.e.,
58 probability of successfully completing the RAP) and access delay. However, most of these ACBC
59 schemes were not designed for cellular networks. Specifically, such a high performance is normally
60 achieved by assuming an idealized ACB scheme and by setting extremely precise barring parameters,
61 for which complex processes and bold assumptions are oftentimes needed. As a consequence, most of
62 the ACBC schemes proposed in the literature cannot be implemented in the cellular systems [9,11,14,
63 17].

64 Tello-Oquendo *et al.* presented one of the few ACBC schemes that were specifically designed for
65 3GPP cellular networks [18]. In particular, reinforcement learning approach was utilized. However,
66 results show that the performance achieved under the most typical mMTC scenario with the proposed
67 ACBC is lower than that of correctly selecting the fixed barring parameters beforehand.

68 In our previous work, we proposed an ACBC scheme that incorporates a filtering block [19]. In
69 this block, the well-known least-mean square (LMS) algorithm was implemented. In particular, two
70 different applications of the LMS were investigated: the adaptive line enhancer (ALE) and a novel
71 twist on the latter, referred to as “pulling” ALE (PALE) [19]; preliminary work on the benefits of
72 the PALE can be found in [8]. Results presented in our previous work illustrate our ACBC scheme
73 is one of the few that can be implemented in 3GPP networks and that can provide a near-optimal
74 performance, which greatly surpasses that of the ACB with fixed parameters, under different access
75 requests intensities [8,19].

76 In this paper, we investigate the potential benefits of implementing the recursive least-squares
77 (RLS) algorithm or fixed finite-duration impulse response (FIR) filters instead of the LMS.

78 The characteristics that differentiate the present work differs from our previous are described in
79 the following.

Figure 1. Random access (RA) in LTE-A: ACB scheme and RA procedure

- 80 1. Two different filtering methods are investigated, namely the recursive least-squares (RLS) adaptive
81 algorithm and a fixed finite-duration impulse response (FIR) filter. The benefits of these methods
82 are compared to those of the LMS. The latter was the only algorithm considered in our previous
83 work.
- 84 2. An in-depth analysis of the tracking capabilities of the LMS and RLS adaptive algorithms in
85 transient environments is presented.

86 Results show that several filtering methods lead to an adequate operation of our ACBC scheme
87 under the most typical mMTC scenario, which in turn increases the success probability from a poor 31%
88 to more than 98% while maintaining a short access delay. The main difference between implementing
89 an adaptive algorithm and a simple FIR filter is that a specific configuration of the former can
90 further reduce the access delay of UEs with no need of an additional mechanism. Conversely, such a
91 mechanism is needed for simple FIR filters. This characteristic of the adaptive algorithms acquires
92 special relevance in mMTC scenarios that can be handled by the RAP itself (i.e., when no congestion is
93 likely to occur), and when increasing the access delay of UEs is not beneficial.

94 The rest of the paper is organized as follows. The RAP and the ACB scheme are described in
95 Section 2. Next, our ACBC scheme, the studied filtering methods, and the methodology used to assess
96 the benefits of these methods are explained in Section 3. Our main results are presented in Section 4
97 and Section 5 concludes the paper.

98 2. Random access procedure (RAP) and access class barring (ACB) scheme

99 This section describes the random access (RA) as defined in the 3GPP standards. It comprises the
100 access control and the contention-based RA procedure (RAP) [1,20]. Throughout this study, the access
101 class barring (ACB), as defined in the 3GPP standards [1], is studied and we assume no other access
102 control scheme is implemented. Figure 1 provides a brief description of the RA in 3GPP networks with
103 the ACB scheme.

104 The first step for a UE to switch from idle to connected mode is to acquire the network
105 configuration parameters. Once these have been obtained, the UE is subject to the ACB scheme and,
106 finally, it performs the RAP. The network operates in a time-slotted channel in which the minimum
107 unit for scheduling is the subframe.

108 The configuration parameters are broadcast by the eNB through the *System Information Blocks*
109 (SIBs). The SIB1 includes, among other parameters, the periodicity of other SIBs in the parameter
110 *si-Periodicity* $\in \{80, 160, \dots, 5120\}$ ms [1]. The SIB2 includes some basic parameters such as the

Algorithm 1 Access class barring (ACB) scheme.

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1: repeat
2:   Select the mean barring time  $t_{\text{acb}}(j)$  and barring rate  $p_{\text{acb}}(j)$  broadcast in the  $j$ th SIB2.
3:   Generate  $\mathcal{U}[0,1) \equiv$  a random number with uniform distribution between 0 and 1.
4:   if  $\mathcal{U}[0,1) \leq p_{\text{acb}}(j)$  then
5:     Initiate the RAP.
6:   else
7:     Generate a new  $\mathcal{U}[0,1)$ .
8:     Select the barring time as

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$$t_{\text{barred}} = (0.7 + 0.6\mathcal{U}[0,1)) t_{\text{acb}}(j). \quad (1)$$

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9:     Wait for  $t_{\text{barred}}$ .
10:  end if
11: until the RAP is initiated.

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111 periodicity of the time/frequency resources in which preamble transmissions are allowed t_{rao} (known
112 as random access opportunities, RAOs) and the barring parameters [1,4,5,21].

113 The j th SIB2 transmission includes a barring rate $p_{\text{acb}}(j)$ and a mean barring time $t_{\text{acb}}(j)$ [1]. Only
114 special categories of high-priority UEs may not be subject to the ACB scheme. The rest of the UEs
115 subject to the ACB scheme must perform a barring check before initiating the RAP (i.e., before the
116 transmission of their first preamble) as described in Algorithm 1 [1,22].

117 UEs that succeed in the barring check are no longer subject to the ACB scheme [23] and proceed
118 to perform the RAP as follows.

119 **Preamble:** Each UE randomly selects one out of the r available preambles and sends it towards
120 the eNB in a RAO through the random access channel (RACH). Multiple UEs can access the eNB in
121 the same RAO using different preambles due to their orthogonality. As a result, eNB decodes the
122 preambles transmitted without (wireless channel) errors by exactly one UE.

123 In this study, we assume the eNB cannot decode preambles transmitted by multiple UEs
124 simultaneously; we refer to these as collided preambles. This assumption goes in line with the
125 3GPP recommendations for the performance analysis of the RACH [2] and with most of the
126 literature [3,14,15,24–27]. The interested reader may refer to [12] for details on the two main
127 assumptions related to collisions during the RAP and their impact on performance.

128 Next, the UE waits for a RA predefined time window, known as the RA response (RAR) window,
129 to receive a RAR message from the eNB.

130 **RAR:** The eNB computes an identifier for each successfully decoded preamble and sends the
131 RAR message through the physical downlink control channel (PDCCH). It includes, among other data,
132 uplink grants for the transmission of Msg3 . Up to one RAR message can be sent per subframe, but it
133 may contain several uplink grants; each of which is associated to a successfully decoded preamble.

134 The PDCCH resources are limited, so a maximum of n_{ug} uplink grants can be sent within a RAR
135 window. Since up to three uplink grants can be sent per subframe in a RAR message, the number of
136 available uplink grants per RAR window depends on its length.

137 **Connection request and contention resolution:** After receiving the corresponding uplink grant,
138 the UEs schedule the transmission of the connection request message to the eNB through dedicated
139 resources. Then, the eNB responds to each connection request with a contention resolution message.
140 the transmission of both of these messages is protected by a hybrid automatic repeat request (HARQ)
141 mechanism.

Figure 2. Block diagram of the RAP with our ACBC scheme. The random access is performed at each RAO, whereas the ACBC can only be performed once every t_{si} RAOs.

142 The maximum number of allowed preamble transmissions for each UE is broadcast by the eNB
 143 through the SIB2 [1]. Access failure can occur, for example due to a preamble collision or due to
 144 wireless channel errors during contention resolution. Whenever an access failure occurs, and if the
 145 maximum number of preamble transmissions has not been reached, the UE waits for a random backoff
 146 time (determined by the backoff indicator); then randomly selects and transmits a new preamble at the
 147 next RAO.

148 3. Access class barring configuration (ACBC) scheme

149 This section describes the structure of our ACBC scheme and the configuration of the selected
 150 filtering methods. It is important to emphasize our ACBC scheme, first introduced in [8], was designed
 151 to operate under the 3GPP specifications, hence, it can be directly implemented in 4G and 5G networks.

152 Figure 2 illustrates the block diagram that describes the operation of the RAP with our ACBC
 153 scheme. Two main blocks are clearly identified in the figure: random access (RA) and ACB
 154 configuration (ACBC). The RA, depicted in the upper part of Figure 2, operates as described in
 155 Section 2.

156 Let $a(i)$ be the number of UEs that attempt to switch from idle to connected mode for the first
 157 time at the i th RAO; these UEs are subject to the ACB scheme. Hereafter we refer to $a(i)$ simply as the
 158 UE arrivals.

159 Next, let $f(i)$ be the number of UEs whose barring check at the i th RAO is successful. These
 160 UEs begin the RAP at the i th RAO; hence, $f(i)$ is also the number of UEs whose first preamble is
 161 transmitted at the i th RAO. Finally, $s(i)$ is the number of UEs that will receive an uplink grant at the
 162 i th RAR window. That is, as a response to a preamble transmitted at the i th RAO. Therefore, The
 163 discrete time index i stands for the epoch number, where the epoch duration is one RAO, since the RA
 164 is performed at each and every RAO.

165 The lower part of Figure 2 depicts the structure of our ACBC scheme, where the eNB calculates the
 166 barring parameters: mean barring time $t_{acb}(j)$ and barring rate $p_{acb}(j)$ that will be broadcast through
 167 the j th SIB2. The SIB2 is broadcast once every t_{si} RAOs, hence, these parameters are adapted according
 168 to the perceived access intensity throughout this period. As such, the discrete time index j stands
 169 for the epoch number when the epoch duration is t_{si} RAOs. Therefore, the ACBC block operates at
 170 a time scale that is t_{si} times greater than that of the RA block. Specifically, the j th SIB2 is broadcast
 171 at the $i = (jt_{si})$ th RAO. Therefore, the barring parameters remain constant from the $(jt_{si} + 1)$ th until
 172 the $((j + 1)t_{si})$ th RAO. Throughout this study we assume $t_{acb}(j)$ is selected beforehand and remains
 173 fixed throughout the operation of the network. Hence, we the latter is simply denoted as t_{acb} . In the
 174 following, we describe the process to calculate $p_{acb}(j)$.

175 The eNB calculates the ratio of idle to available resources immediately before the j th SIB2
 176 transmission. For this, let $n(i)$ be the number of contending UEs (i.e., total number of preamble
 177 transmissions) at the i th RAO. Next, please observe the number of successful preambles at an arbitrary
 178 RAO i is a random variable. The theoretical PRACH (uplink) capacity can be defined as the maximum
 179 expected value of the latter random variable for a given number of available preambles r and for any
 180 $n(i) \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$. The PRACH capacity is achieved when the number of contending UEs is

$$n^*(i) = \left[\log \left(\frac{r}{r-1} \right) \right]^{-1} \quad (2)$$

181 and is calculated by Lin *et al.* [15] as follows.

$$c(r) = n^*(i) \left(1 - \frac{1}{r} \right)^{n^*(i)-1}. \quad (3)$$

182 Next, let $c(r, n_{\text{ug}})$ be the theoretical capacity of the channels involved in the RAP: PRACH and
 183 PDCCH. The capacity of the PDCCH is exclusively determined by the number of available uplink
 184 grants per RAR window n_{ug} [2]. Hence, the capacity of the RAP is the minimum between the PRACH
 185 capacity and the PDCCH capacity,

$$c(r, n_{\text{ug}}) = \min \{ c(r), n_{\text{ug}} \}. \quad (4)$$

186 We refer to $c(r, n_{\text{ug}})$ simply as the RAP capacity.

With this information, the ratio of idle to available resources is calculated immediately before the
 j th SIB2 transmission (i.e., at the (jt_{si}) th RAO) by means of the scaling filter block and the comparator
 shown in the bottom right corner of Fig. 2 as

$$u(j) = 1 - \mathbf{h}^T \mathbf{s}(j) \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{h} = [h_0, h_1, \dots, h_{t_{\text{si}}-1}]$ is the column vector of coefficients of the scaling filter

$$h_m = \frac{1}{t_{\text{si}} c(r, n_{\text{ug}})}, \quad \text{for } m \in \{0, 1, \dots, t_{\text{si}}\} \quad (6)$$

and $\mathbf{s}(j) = [s(jt_{\text{si}}), s(jt_{\text{si}} - 1), \dots, s(jt_{\text{si}} - t_{\text{si}})]$ is the vector that contains the number of uplink grants
 assigned at each of the t_{si} RAOs within the SIB2 period. Next, $u(j)$ serves as the input to the filtering
 process, whose output $y(j)$ is used to calculate the barring rate for the j th SIB2 broadcast interval

$$p_{\text{acb}}(j) = \min \{ y(j), 1 \}. \quad (7)$$

187 Hence, $p_{\text{acb}}(j)$ decreases with the ratio of idle to available resources. This increases the probability of
 188 delaying the beginning of the RAP when most of the resources have been utilized.

189 The filtering block in our ACBC (at the bottom of Figure 2) is generic, which means different
 190 filtering methods can be implemented at this point. In the following, we describe two three possibilities:
 191 two adaptive filtering algorithms and FIR filters with fixed coefficients.

192 3.1. Recursive least-squares (RLS) algorithm

193 The recursive least-squares (RLS) algorithm is renown for its fast rate of convergence. For
 194 instance, the rate of convergence of the RLS can be up to an order of magnitude faster than that of other
 195 algorithms, such as the least-mean square (LMS, described in the next subsection) [28]. In particular,
 196 the RLS is a recursive implementation of the method of *least squares*, and its numerical complexity is in
 197 the order of $\mathcal{O}(M^2)$. Nevertheless, the mathematical formulation and implementation of the RLS is
 198 relatively simple [28].

Figure 3. Block diagram of the RLS adaptive filter algorithm.

Algorithm 2 RLS adaptive algorithm.

Require: the number of filter coefficients M

Require: regularization parameter $\delta > 0$

Require: forgetting factor λ

- 1: Initialize the vector of filter coefficients $w(0)$ and the input vector $u(0)$ as

$$w_m(0) = u(-m) = 0, \quad m \in \{0, 1, \dots, M-1\} \quad (9)$$

- 2: Initialize the inverse correlation matrix $P(0) = \delta^{-1} I$

- 3: **for all** $j = 1, 2, \dots$ **do**

- 4: Filtering process:

$$y(j) = w^T(j-1)u(j) \quad (10)$$

- 5: Adaptive process:

$$k(j) = \frac{\lambda^{-1} P(j-1) u(j)}{1 + \lambda^{-1} u^T(j) P(j-1) u(j)} \quad (11a)$$

$$\xi(j) = d(j) - w^T(j-1) u(j) \quad (11b)$$

$$w(j) = w(j-1) + k(j)\xi(j) \quad (11c)$$

$$P(j) = \lambda^{-1} P(j-1) - \lambda^{-1} k(j) u^T(j) P(j-1) \quad (11d)$$

- 6: **end for**
-

199 The internal structure of the RLS algorithm is illustrated in Figure 3. A buffer has been
200 incorporated to clearly illustrate that the ratio of idle resources during the last M SIB2 intervals

$$u(j) = [u(j), u(j-1), \dots, u(j-M+1)] \quad (8)$$

201 is the input to the algorithm. That is, a single value of $u(j)$ is the input to the buffer as indicated
202 by the thin arrow, and the output of the buffer is a vector, as indicated by the thick arrows.

203 The RLS is summarized in Algorithm 6, and consists of a filtering and an adaptive process.

204 In the filtering process, the output of a finite-duration impulse response (FIR) filter $y(j)$ is
205 computed from $u(j)$.

In the adaptive process, the output $y(j)$ is compared to the desired response $d(j)$ to adapt the weights of the FIR filter

$$w(j) = [w_0(j), w_1(j), \dots, w_{M-1}(j)]. \quad (12)$$

Figure 4. Block diagram of the LMS adaptive algorithm.

206 The parameter $\zeta(j)$ is the *a priori* estimation error, which represents an estimate of the desired
 207 response $d(j)$ based on the old least-squares estimate of $w(j-1)$. It is essential to emphasize that
 208 $\zeta(j)$ is different to the *a posteriori* estimation error $e(j)$, calculated in the LMS algorithm (see next
 209 subsection).

210 Regarding the configuration of the RLS in our ACBC scheme, the desired response is set to be
 211 $d(j) = 1$ for all j . The reason for this is that no signal correlated to the variations of $u(j)$ is available.
 212 Furthermore, selecting $d(j)$ to its maximum possible value causes the RLS algorithm to minimize the
 213 distance between the output $y(j)$ and $d(j) = 1$, which in turn “pulls” the output toward its maximum
 214 value. This increases the barring rate $p_{acb}(j)$ and, in turn, reduces the access delay of UEs. This effect
 215 will be observed in Figure 5 on page 12.

216 The RLS algorithm has two parameters that must be selected empirically, the regularization
 217 parameter δ and the forgetting factor λ . The latter determines the rate at which the algorithm
 218 “forgets” the previous inputs. There is no exact method to select δ nor λ . However, the following
 219 recommendations exist.

- 220 • Regularization parameter δ : Select a small positive value when the input (in our case $u(j)$) is
 221 relatively high with respect to its sudden variations. Select a large positive value otherwise.
- 222 • Forgetting factor λ : Select a positive value that is close to, but less than, 1. This ensures past
 223 values of the input $u(j)$ are forgotten by the algorithm. On the other hand, $\lambda = 1$ corresponds to
 224 the method of least squares.

225 The beginning of Section 4 focuses on finding adequate values for δ and λ .

226 3.2. Least-mean square (LMS) algorithm

227 The least-mean square (LMS) algorithm is widely used because of its simplicity and numerical
 228 robustness [28]. Concretely, the complexity of the LMS scales linearly with the filter length M . The
 229 LMS is an application of the method of *stochastic gradient descent*, hence, it belongs to a different family
 230 of algorithms to that of the RLS.

231 The internal structure of the LMS is depicted in Figure 4 and Algorithm 3 summarizes its operation.

232 As with the RLS, the LMS comprises a filtering and an adaptive process. An important difference
 233 between these two algorithms is that the output $y(j)$ is compared to the desired response $d(j)$ to obtain
 234 the error $e(j)$ in the LMS, whereas the *a priori* error ζ is calculated in the RLS.

235 The correct selection of the rate of adjustment μ is essential for the LMS to be stable. In particular,
 236 the μ must be selected to satisfy

$$0 < \frac{1}{2}\mu\|u(j)\|^2 < 1, \quad \text{for all } u(j) \quad (16)$$

237 where $\|\cdot\|$ is the Euclidean norm operator.

238 Two different configurations of the LMS algorithm are considered: an adaptive line enhancer
 239 (ALE) and a “pulling” ALE (PALE). In the ALE, the primary input is a delayed version of $u(j)$, namely

Algorithm 3 LMS adaptive algorithm.

Require: the number of filter coefficients M **Require:** the adaptation step size μ 1: Initialize the vector of filter coefficients $\mathbf{w}(0)$ and the input vector $\mathbf{u}(0)$ as

$$w_m(0) = u(-m) = 0, \quad m \in \{0, 1, \dots, M-1\} \quad (13)$$

2: **for all** $j = 1, 2, \dots$ **do**3: Select the desired response $d(j)$

4: Filtering process:

$$y(j) = \mathbf{w}^T(j)\mathbf{u}(j) \quad (14)$$

5: Adaptive process:

$$e(j) = d(j) - y(j) \quad (15a)$$

$$\mathbf{w}(j+1) = \mathbf{w}(j) + \mu e(j)\mathbf{u}(j) \quad (15b)$$

6: **end for**

240 $\mathbf{u}(j-1)$, while the desired output is set to $d(j) = u(j)$. In the PALE, the primary input is simply $u(j)$
 241 and the desired output is set to $d(j) = 1$ for all j . The latter configuration has a similar effect on the
 242 filter output as the one described above for the RLS configuration.

243 *3.3. Simple low-pass FIR filter*

244 Besides investigating the benefits of our ACBC scheme with the two previously described adaptive
 245 filter algorithms, we also consider the inclusion of a simple finite-duration impulse response (FIR)
 246 filter with fixed weights w_m . We refer to this as the low-pass filtering (LPF) method.

The filter weights must be chosen to ensure the following two conditions are met.

$$\sum_{m=0}^{M-1} w_m = 1 \quad (17a)$$

$$w_m > 0 \quad \forall m \in \{0, 1, \dots, M-1\}. \quad (17b)$$

247 For this, let ρ be the degree of the decreasing polynomial function that determines the fixed
 248 weights of the filter. Naturally, the rapidness of the response of the fixed filter to sudden changes in
 249 the input $u(j)$ increases with ρ , but so does its sensitivity. In other words, the selection of ρ creates a
 250 tradeoff between the responsiveness and the stability of the filter output.

In particular, we choose the filter weights as

$$w_m = (M-m)^\rho \left(\sum_{m=0}^{M-1} (M-m)^\rho \right)^{-1} = (M-m)^\rho \left(\sum_{\ell=1}^M \ell^\rho \right)^{-1}; \quad (18)$$

251 where $\sum_{\ell=1}^M \ell^\rho$ is the normalization factor.

252 *3.4. Methodology*

253 In this study, we aim to compare the tracking capabilities of the RLS adaptive algorithm to
 254 those of the LMS and simple fixed FIR filters in a transient environment: the traffic model 2 [2]. The

Table 1. Characteristics of the different traffic models defined by the 3GPP for the performance evaluation of the RAP [2].

Parameter	Traffic model 1	Traffic model 2
Number of UEs n	30 000	30 000
Distribution period t_{dist} (s)	60	10
Distribution over t_{dist}	Uniform	Beta(3,4)

Table 2. Parameters for the selected network configuration.

Parameter	Setting
Available preambles	$r = 54$
Subframe length	1 ms
RAO periodicity	$t_{\text{rao}} = 5$ subframes
RAR window size	5 subframes
Available uplink grants per RAR window	$n_{\text{ug}} = 15$
Period of SIB transmissions	80 ms
SIB2 periodicity in RAOs	$t_{\text{si}} = 16$
Maximum number of preamble transmissions	10
Backoff indicator	20 ms
Detection probability for the k th preamble transmission	$P_d(k) = 1 - 1/e^k$
Maximum number of <i>Msg3</i> and <i>Msg4</i> transmissions	5
Detection probability for <i>Msg3</i> and <i>Msg4</i>	0.9

255 latter represents a highly synchronized mMTC scenario, in which the UE arrivals follow a Beta (3,4)
 256 distribution over 10 s. Several studies have confirmed the traffic model 2 leads to severe congestion if
 257 no access control scheme is implemented [2–5,13,29].

258 Results presented in the following section are obtained by simulation. In particular, a C-based
 259 simulator is used, which closely replicates the arrival process of the UEs, the ACB scheme, and the
 260 RAP as described in the specifications [1,22]. In each simulation, the adaptive algorithm is initialized
 261 and the filter weights are stabilized (if applicable). Then, $n = 30\,000$ UE arrivals are scheduled within
 262 the distribution period t_{dist} which begins at $i = 0$. The j th SIB2 is broadcast at the $(jt_{\text{si}} + i_r)$ th RAO,
 263 where i_r is a discrete random time shift, selected from a uniform distribution between 0 and $t_{\text{si}} - 1$.
 264 A simulation run is concluded when every UE has terminated the RA procedure. The number of
 265 simulation runs is set to the smallest number that ensures the cumulative results obtained up to the
 266 last simulation differ from those obtained up to the previous simulation by less than 0.01 percent.

267 The first step in our analyses is to use a non-synchronized mMTC scenario, the traffic model
 268 1, to identify an adequate configuration of the RLS algorithm. The traffic model 1 can be seen as a
 269 stationary scenario of finite duration with a low access intensity, in which UE arrivals follow a uniform
 270 distribution over 60 s. As such, the traffic model 1 (stationary scenario) is used to “train” the RLS
 271 algorithm to provide an adequate response in a transient scenario. For this, we set the UEs to ignore
 272 the ACB scheme and assess two main characteristics: the rate of convergence of the output of the filter
 273 and the relative amplitude of its variations with respect to the mean value. The main characteristics of
 274 both traffic models are listed in Table 1.

275 In our experiments, we assume the most typical configuration of the RACH, as suggested by
 276 the 3GPP [2]. The number of available preambles is set to $r = 54$; this is the most typical value for
 277 this parameter. Furthermore, it allows us to evaluate the RAP in an scenario in which the number of
 278 successful accesses is greatly affected by r , but also by the number of available uplink grants n_{ug} . In
 279 addition, we assume the shortest possible period for the SIB transmissions, 80 ms. These values are
 280 listed in Table 2, along with other values selected for the most relevant configuration parameters.

Table 3. Parameters for the selected filter configurations.

	Parameter	Setting
Common to all		
	Number of filter coefficients	$M = 32$
	Mean barring time	$t_{\text{acb}} = 1 \text{ s}$
RLS		
	Forgetting factor	$\lambda \in \{0.99, 0.999, 1\}$
	Regularization parameter	$\delta \in \{10, 1, 0.1, 0.01, 0.001\}$
	Primary input	$u(j)$
	Desired response	$d(j) = 1$
LMS ALE		
	Adaptation step size	$\mu = 1/800$
	Primary input	$u(j - 1)$
	Desired response	$d(j) = u(j)$
LMS PALE		
	Adaptation step size	$\mu = 1/800$
	Primary input	$u(j)$
	Desired response	$d(j) = 1$
LPF		
	Polynomial degree	$\rho \in \{0, 1, 2\}$

281 To assess the benefits of the RLS algorithm, we test several values for parameter δ and λ , whereas
 282 other configuration parameters remain fixed. For example, $M = 32$ is a widely used filter length that
 283 led to satisfactory results in our preliminary tests with the RLS algorithm. Furthermore, it is the filter
 284 length that maximizes the benefits of the LMS algorithm [19]. Therefore, it is selected throughout the
 285 remainder of the paper for every filter.

286 In addition, we select an intuitive value for the mean barring rate $t_{\text{acb}} = 1 \text{ s}$; as it will be seen
 287 throughout the following section, this value leads to a sufficiently high $P_s \geq 0.95$ for all the selected
 288 filtering methods under the traffic model 2. Certainly, an optimal value for this parameter could be
 289 selected, but it is out of the scope of this paper to optimize the performance of each of the studied
 290 filtering methods under the selected scenario. The interested reader may refer to [19], where our
 291 ACBC scheme with the LMS algorithm was optimized, and apply an analogous procedure for the RLS
 292 algorithm.

293 The configuration parameters for the filtering methods studied in this paper are listed in Table 3.

294 In particular, we are set to find configurations of the RLS and fixed FIR filters that successfully
 295 reduce the variations of $u(j)$ with the fastest possible convergence toward $\mathbb{E}[u(j)]$. Under the traffic
 296 model 1, $n = 30\,000$ UE accesses are uniformly distributed within 60 s. Since RAOs occur once every
 297 $t_{\text{rao}} = 5$ subframes and the subframe duration is i ms, there are $i_{\text{dist}} = 12\,000$ RAOs in the distribution
 298 period.

Please let A be the RV that defines the number of UE accesses at an arbitrary RAO within the
 distribution period. Hence, $a(i)$, shown in Figure 2, is the outcome of a single experiment for RV A
 at the i th RAO. Please observe $A \sim B(n, 1/i_{\text{dist}})$, hence, we have $\mathbb{E}[A] = n/i_{\text{dist}} = 2.5$. From there,
 $\mathbb{E}[u(j)]$ can be approximated by substituting $s(i)$ with \mathbf{a} , a column vector of length t_{si} whose entries
 are $\mathbb{E}[A]$, in (5).

$$\mathbb{E}[u(j)] \approx 1 - \mathbf{h}^T \mathbf{a} = 1 - \frac{\mathbb{E}[A]}{c(r, n_{\text{ug}})} \quad (19)$$

299 which gives $\mathbb{E}[u(j)] \approx 5/6$ for $r = 54$. This value has been confirmed by simulation and by an
 300 analytical model [12].

Figure 5. Ratio of idle to available resources $u(j)$ and barring rate $p_{\text{acb}}(j)$ calculated at the j th SIB2 for a single simulation run and $r = 54$ for the RLS algorithm with $\lambda = \{0.99, 0.999, 1\}$ and (a) $\delta = 0.001$; (b) $\delta = 0.01$; (c) $\delta = 0.1$; and (d) $\delta = 1$. The horizontal line is located at $\mathbb{E}[u(j)]$.

301 4. Results

302 In this section, we assess the benefits of our ACBC scheme with different filtering methods. As a
 303 starting point, we find adequate values for the regularization parameter δ and the forgetting factor
 304 λ , which determine the response of the RLS algorithm. Next, we briefly study the response of the
 305 LPF method (fixed FIR filters) and of the LMS algorithm. Next, we assess the benefits provided by
 306 the different filtering methods under the traffic model 2, when compared to an ACB scheme with
 307 fixed parameters (static ACB) and to our ACBC scheme with no filtering (i.e., where $y(j) = u(j)$). The
 308 section concludes with the comparison of the response of the different filtering methods under the
 309 traffic model 2.

310 Adequate values for parameters δ and λ are selected by observing the response of the algorithm.
 311 The latter is illustrated in Figure 5 for $\delta \in \{0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1\}$ and $\lambda \in \{0.99, 0.999, 1\}$, given $r = 54$,
 312 along with the calculated $u(j)$. Clearly, the response is not adequate with $\lambda = 0.99$ as $p_{\text{acb}}(j)$ presents
 313 a drastic drop around $j = M$, hence, the response of the RLS is not stable. On the other hand, the
 314 difference in the response between selecting $\lambda = 0.999$ and $\lambda = 1$ is minimal; both of these values of
 315 λ greatly reduce the variations of $p_{\text{acb}}(j)$ given a sufficiently low value of δ is selected, for example,
 316 $\delta = 0.001$. Figure 5 shows $\delta = 0.01$ is also an acceptable candidate for the regularization parameter,
 317 whereas higher values of δ should be avoided, as the amplitude of variations of $p_{\text{acb}}(j)$ is high when
 318 compared to its mean.

319 It has been observed in the literature that parameter λ plays a similar role in the RLS algorithm
 320 as the complement of parameter μ in the LMS algorithm [28]. In our previous studies we observed
 321 $\mu = 1/800$ is an adequate value for the adaptation step size in our ACBC scheme. Hence, results
 322 presented in Figure 5 confirm the relation between λ and μ , as an adequate response is obtained with
 323 $\lambda = 0.999 \approx 1 - 1/800 = 1 - \mu$. The latter value of λ is selected throughout the remainder of the

Figure 6. Ratio of idle to available resources $u(j)$ and barring rate $p_{\text{acb}}(j)$ calculated at the j th SIB2 for a single simulation run and $r = 54$ under the traffic model 1 for the (a) LPF approach with $\rho \in \{0, 1, 2\}$ and (b) the LMS algorithm. The horizontal line is located at $\mathbb{E}[u(j)]$.

paper, in combination of $\delta = 0.001$. As it can be seen, $p_{\text{acb}}(j)$ with this combination converges toward $\mathbb{E}[u(j)]$ around $j = M$.

Regarding the LPF method, it is immediate to see in Figure 6 that $p_{\text{acb}}(j)$ converges toward $\mathbb{E}[u(j)]$ at exactly $j = M$ for $\rho = 0$, and the rate of convergence increases slightly with ρ . It is also interesting to observe that the $p_{\text{acb}}(j)$ calculated with the RLS, given $\lambda = 0.999$ and $\delta = 0.1$, shown in Figure 5b, is highly similar to that of the LPF method. On the other hand, the $p_{\text{acb}}(j)$ calculated with the LMS presents a different behavior to both the RLS and LPF methods. For example, $p_{\text{acb}}(M) < \mathbb{E}[u(j)]$ and converges toward $\mathbb{E}[u(j)]$ approximately until $j = 100$.

Next, we investigate whether the difference in the response of the filters provides different benefits to our ACBC scheme. For this, we consider three key performance indicators:

- Success probability, defined as the probability to successfully complete the RAP. The minimum success probability considered as acceptable is 0.95. Hence, the main goal of our ACBC scheme is to guarantee that more than 95% of the UEs successfully complete the RAP.
- Access delay, defined as the time elapsed since the arrival of an specific UE and the successful completion of its RAP. This KPI is assessed in terms of the 95th percentile. That is, the delay of 95% of the UEs that successfully complete the RAP is lower than, or equal, to the reported value.
- Number of preamble transmissions to successfully complete the RAP. This KPI is assessed in terms of its expected value.

It is important to emphasize that the success probability under the traffic model 2 with no implemented ACB scheme is only 0.313, which is poor. In addition, the benefits of our ACBC scheme are minor when no filtering is performed and $y(j) = u(j)$. Specifically, the success probability with $t_{\text{acb}} = 1$ s and no filtering is only 0.419, which is still unacceptable. The reason for such a poor performance is that the UE arrivals and the number of successful accesses per RAO present high variations with respect to their mean value. These variations remain present in $u(j)$ and, naturally, in $p_{\text{acb}}(j)$. On the other hand, filtering away these variations in $u(j)$ leads to a stable $p_{\text{acb}}(j)$ that is closely related to the intensity of UE accesses in a larger time scale to that of the SIB2 period.

Figure 7 shows the 95th percentile of access delay and the expected number of preamble transmissions for the studied filtering methods. The success probability obtained with each of the filtering methods included in Figure 7 is higher than 0.985, hence, the difference between them, in this KPI, is negligible. For benchmark purposes, Figure 7 also includes the KPIs obtained with the optimal configuration of a static ACB. The optimal configuration for the latter is defined as the combination of fixed barring parameters that leads to a success probability of 0.95 or higher with the shortest 95th percentile of access delay. Hence, the success probability obtained with the static ACB is 0.95.

Figure 7. 95th percentile of access delay and expected number of preamble transmissions obtained with our ACBC scheme and with each of the studied filtering methods; the KPIs obtained with the optimal configuration of an ACB scheme with fixed parameters (static ACB) are also included. The success probability for these is higher than 0.95.

357 As it can be seen, regardless of the selected filtering method, the 95th percentile of access delay
 358 and the expected number of preamble transmissions are reduced by more than 26% and 12% when
 359 compared to the optimal static ACB implementation, respectively. It can also be seen in Figure 7 that
 360 the different values of ρ for the LPF method have a minimal impact on performance. Specifically, the
 361 difference in each of the two KPIs shown in the figure for the different valued of ρ is less than 4%.

362 On the other hand, there is a significant difference between the KPIs obtained with each of the
 363 adaptive algorithm configurations. In particular, the ALE leads to the longest access delay but to the
 364 lowest number of transmissions, and the opposite occurs with the PALE. The RLS leads to an access
 365 delay that is in between both LMS configurations, but to the highest number of preamble transmissions.
 366 This difference is caused by the “pulling” effect of the PALE and RLS algorithms, which is absent from
 367 the ALE.

368 Figure 8 clearly illustrates the difference in the $p_{\text{acb}}(j)$ calculated with the resemblance of the
 369 latter with the different values of $\rho \in \{0, 2\}$. The number of UE arrivals and successful accesses with
 370 the RLS algorithm at each RAO is also illustrated as a reference. Specifically, Figure 8b showcases the
 371 ALE operates as a low-pass filter for $p_{\text{acb}}(j)$, whereas the PALE and the RLS “pull” the latter toward
 372 $d(j) = 1$. However, it is important to observe that the “pulling” effect is greater for the PALE than for
 373 the RLS. For instance, $p_{\text{acb}}(j)$ increases more rapidly for the PALE than for the RLS as the number of
 374 UE arrivals drops (i.e., after the 2000th RAO, which corresponds to the 150th SIB2 transmission). The
 375 reason for this effect is the rapid response of the RLS, which converges more rapidly toward $\mathbb{E}[u(j)]$,
 376 calculated with the M most recent values of $u(j)$. As a result, the benefits provided by the RLS are in
 377 between those provided by the ALE and the PALE.

378 On the other hand, the calculated $p_{\text{acb}}(j)$ with both $\rho \in \{0, 2\}$ is closely similar in the period
 379 $j \in [50, 175]$, and the difference is observed when rapid changes in the number of successful accesses
 380 occur. Naturally, the rate of change of $p_{\text{acb}}(j)$ with respect of $s(i)$ is more rapid for $\rho = 2$ than for $\rho = 0$.
 381 However, this difference is not evident in the 95th percentile of access delay, illustrated in Figure 7.

382 5. Conclusions

383 In this paper we investigated the impact of implementing different filtering methods to our ACBC
 384 scheme under a typical mMTC scenario: the traffic model 2. The latter leads to severe congestion when
 385 no access control scheme is implemented.

386 Based on the behavior described in the Section 4, it is safe to claim our ACBC scheme can operate
 387 efficiently with several filtering methods, and its performance is compromised only if this process is
 388 omitted. That is, when compared to the optimal configuration of an static ACB scheme, our ACBC
 389 scheme can reduce the 95th percentile of access delay by more than 26%, while increasing the success
 390 probability and reducing the number of preamble transmissions with numerous filtering methods.

Figure 8. (a) Number of UE arrivals $a(i)$ and successful accesses $s(i)$ per RAO with the RLS algorithms, and barring rate $p_{acb}(j)$ calculated at the j th SIB2 for a single simulation run and $r = 54$ under the traffic model 2 with the (b) RLS, ALE LMS, and PALE LMS and (c) LPF with $\rho \in \{0, 2\}$. Results derived from a single simulation.

391 One of the main advantages of selecting an adaptive algorithm, such as the LMS and the RLS,
 392 is the “pulling” effect provided by setting the desired response to 1. By doing so, the access delay of
 393 UEs is further reduced. The latter is of utmost importance under scenarios in which the number of
 394 UE accesses is considerably low when compared to the RAP capacity, such as the traffic model 1. In
 395 these scenarios, an access control scheme is not needed and increasing the access delay of UEs may
 396 be counterproductive. On the other hand, correctly configuring the LMS and RLS algorithms is not
 397 straightforward and different methods to reduce the access delay in these scenarios exist. For example,
 398 the mean barring time can be set to be a function of the barring rate, hence reducing the barring time as
 399 the barring rate increases. Furthermore, if the access delay is not relevant at all, implementing a simple
 400 FIR filter in our ACBC scheme would be equally effective as implementing an adaptive algorithm, but
 401 the former eliminates the difficulty of selecting correct configuration parameters.

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409 References

- 410 1. 3GPP. Radio resource control (RRC); Protocol specification, TS 36.331 V15.3.0, 2018.
- 411 2. 3GPP. Study on RAN improvements for machine-type communications, TR 37.868, 2011.
- 412 3. Wei, C.H.; Bianchi, G.; Cheng, R.G. Modeling and analysis of random access channels with
413 bursty arrivals in OFDMA wireless networks. *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.* **2015**, *14*, 1940–1953.
414 doi:10.1109/TWC.2014.2377121.
- 415 4. Laya, A.; Alonso, L.; Alonso-Zarate, J. Is the random access channel of LTE and LTE-A suitable
416 for M2M Communications? A survey of alternatives. *IEEE Commun. Surveys Tuts.* **2014**, *16*, 4–16.
417 doi:10.1109/SURV.2013.111313.00244.
- 418 5. Biral, A.; Centenaro, M.; Zanella, A.; Vangelista, L.; Zorzi, M. The challenges of M2M massive access in
419 wireless cellular networks. *Digit. Commun. Networks* **2015**, *1*, 1–19.
- 420 6. Soltanmohammadi, E.; Ghavami, K.; Naraghi-Pour, M. A survey of traffic issues in machine-to-machine
421 communications over LTE. *IEEE Internet Things J.* **2016**, *3*, 865–884. doi:10.1109/JIOT.2016.2533541.
- 422 7. Wang, Y.P.E.; Lin, X.; Adhikary, A.; Grovlen, A.; Sui, Y.; Blankenship, Y.; Bergman, J.; Razaghi,
423 H.S. A primer on 3GPP narrowband Internet of Things. *IEEE Commun. Mag.* **2017**, *55*, 117–123.
424 doi:10.1109/MCOM.2017.1600510CM.
- 425 8. Leyva-Mayorga, I.; Rodriguez-Hernandez, M.A.; Pla, V.; Martinez-Bauset, J.; Tello-Oquendo, L. An
426 adaptive access class barring scheme for handling massive M2M communications in LTE-A. Proc. Eur.
427 Wireless Conf., 2017, pp. 143–148.
- 428 9. Duan, S.; Shah-Mansouri, V.; Wang, Z.; Wong, V.W.S. D-ACB: Adaptive congestion control algorithm
429 for bursty M2M traffic in LTE networks. *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.* **2016**, *65*, 9847–9861.
430 doi:10.1109/TVT.2016.2527601.
- 431 10. Ferdouse, L.; Anpalagan, A.; Misra, S. Congestion and overload control techniques in massive M2M
432 systems: A survey. *Trans. Emerg. Telecommun. Technol.* **2015**, *28*, e2936. doi:10.1002/ett.2936.
- 433 11. Abbas, R.; Shirvanimoghaddam, M.; Li, Y.; Vucetic, B. Random access for M2M communications with QoS
434 guarantees. *IEEE Trans. Commun.* **2017**, *65*, 2889–2903. doi:10.1109/TCOMM.2017.2690900.
- 435 12. Leyva-Mayorga, I.; Tello-Oquendo, L.; Pla, V.; Martinez-Bauset, J.; Casares-Giner, V. On the accurate
436 performance evaluation of the LTE-A random access procedure and the access class barring scheme. *IEEE*
437 *Trans. Wireless Commun.* **2017**, *16*, 7785–7799. doi:10.1109/TWC.2017.2753784.
- 438 13. Tello-Oquendo, L.; Leyva-Mayorga, I.; Pla, V.; Martinez-Bauset, J.; Vidal, J.R.; Casares-Giner, V.; Guijarro, L.
439 Performance analysis and optimal access class barring parameter configuration in LTE-A networks with
440 massive M2M traffic. *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.* **2018**, *67*, 3505–3520. doi:10.1109/TVT.2017.2776868.
- 441 14. Tavana, M.; Rahmati, A.; Shah-Mansouri, V. Congestion control with adaptive access class barring for LTE
442 M2M overload using Kalman filters. *Comput. Netw.* **2018**, *141*, 222–233. doi:10.1016/j.comnet.2018.01.044.
- 443 15. Lin, T.M.; Lee, C.H.; Cheng, J.P.; Chen, W.T. PRADA: Prioritized random access with dynamic
444 access barring for MTC in 3GPP LTE-A networks. *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.* **2014**, *63*, 2467–2472.
445 doi:10.1109/TVT.2013.2290128.
- 446 16. de Andrade, T.P.C.; Astudillo, C.A.; Sekijima, L.R.; da Fonseca, N.L.S. The random access procedure
447 in Long Term Evolution networks for the Internet of Things. *IEEE Commun. Mag.* **2017**, *55*, 124–131.
448 doi:10.1109/MCOM.2017.1600555CM.
- 449 17. Wang, Z.; Wong, V.W.S. Optimal access class barring for stationary machine type communication
450 devices with timing advance information. *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.* **2015**, *14*, 5374–5387.
451 doi:10.1109/TWC.2015.2437872.
- 452 18. Tello-Oquendo, L.; Pacheco-Paramo, D.; Pla, V.; Martinez-Bauset, J. Reinforcement Learning-Based ACB
453 in LTE-A Networks for Handling Massive M2M and H2H Communications. *IEEE Int. Conf. Commun.*
454 (ICC), 2018, Vol. 2018-May, pp. 1–7. doi:10.1109/ICC.2018.8422167.

- 455 19. Leyva-Mayorga, I.; Rodriguez-Hernandez, M.A.; Pla, V.; Martinez-Bauset, J.; Tello-Oquendo, L. Adaptive
456 access class barring for efficient mMTC. submitted for publication.
- 457 20. 3GPP. Medium access control (MAC) protocol specification, TS 36.321 V15.2.0, 2018.
- 458 21. 3GPP. Physical channels and modulation, TS 36.211 V14.2.0, 2017.
- 459 22. 3GPP. Service accessibility, TS 22.011 V13.6.0, 2016.
- 460 23. Kalalas, C.; Alonso-Zarate, J. Reliability analysis of the random access channel of LTE with access class
461 barring for smart grid monitoring traffic. Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Commun. (ICC) Workshops, 2017, pp.
462 724–730. doi:10.1109/ICCW.2017.7962744.
- 463 24. Leyva-Mayorga, I.; Tello-Oquendo, L.; Pla, V.; Martinez-Bauset, J.; Casares-Giner, V. Performance analysis
464 of access class barring for handling massive M2M traffic in LTE-A networks. Proc. IEEE Int. Conf.
465 Commun. (ICC), 2016, pp. 1–6. doi:10.1109/ICC.2016.7510814.
- 466 25. Arouk, O.; Ksentini, A. General model for RACH procedure performance analysis. *IEEE Commun. Lett.*
467 **2016**, *20*, 372–375. doi:10.1109/LCOMM.2015.2505280.
- 468 26. Zhang, Z.; Chao, H.; Wang, W.; Li, X. Performance analysis and UE-side improvement of extended access
469 barring for machine type communications in LTE. Proc. IEEE Veh. Technol. Conf. (VTC Spring), 2014, pp.
470 1–5. doi:10.1109/VTCspring.2014.7023042.
- 471 27. Cheng, R.G.; Chen, J.; Chen, D.W.; Wei, C.H. Modeling and analysis of an extended access barring
472 algorithm for machine-type communications in LTE-A networks. *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.* **2015**,
473 *14*, 2956–2968. doi:10.1109/TWC.2015.2398858.
- 474 28. Haykin, S. *Adaptive filter theory*, 4 ed.; Prentice Hall: NJ, USA, 2002.
- 475 29. Leyva-Mayorga, I.; Torre, R.; Pandi, S.; Nguyen, G.T.; Pla, V.; Martinez-Bauset, J.; Fitzek, F.H.P. A
476 Network-coded Cooperation Protocol for Efficient Massive Content Distribution. Proc. IEEE Global
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478 **Sample Availability:** Samples of the compounds are available from the authors.

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